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“A STUDY TO ASSESS THE UTILIZATION PATTERN OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR THE TREATMENT OF LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTION IN THE PEDIATRIC DEPARTMENT OF A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL”

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ABSTRACT

Drug utilization research was defined by WHO in 1977 as the "marketing, distribution, prescription and the use of drugs in the society with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social and economic consequences". Drug utilization plays a significant role in helping the health-care system to understand, interpret and improve the prescribing administration and use of medications. Drug utilization research provides insight to different aspects of drug use and drug prescribing such as pattern of use, quality of use and outcomes of drug use. The objective of this study is to assess the prescribing and utilization pattern of antibiotics prescribed to the patients with LRTI admitted in Pediatric Department. A Prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere. Data of pediatric patients collected from the Pediatric ward were included in the study. The collected data was analyzed using Microsoft excel. The DDD/1000 inhabitants/day was also calculated. The medication order problem like possible drug-drug interaction is also evaluated. In our study a total of 150 patients were enrolled. Out of the 150 cases, 88patients (58.67%) were males and 62 patients (41.33%) were females. Pneumonia cases (97) were found to be more when compared to all other forms of LRTI. The most commonly found associated illness was anaemia. The average number of antibiotics per prescription was 1.23 and the average hospital stay was 5.7 ± 2.3 days. The mostly prescribed antibiotic was Amoxicillin followed by Ceftriaxone. Most of the drugs were prescribed through parenteral route. That is, 96.22% of the drugs were prescribed through parenteral route and 3.78% were prescribed through oral route. Out of the 150 cases only 14 cases were subjected for performing culture sensitivity test. In our study, a total of 38 interactions were found. In that 4 major, 9 moderate and 25 minor interactions were found. The PDD and DDD of the antibiotics were also compared. Drug utilization studies have the potential to make objective evaluation and analysis of health professionals work and provide them with feedback to stimulate thinking about their practice and looking for ways to improve their own performance. These studies should become a method of increasing job satisfaction and means of education for health professionals, rather than being perceived as threat or another bureaucratic burden.

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INTRODUCTION

Drug utilization research was defined by WHO in 1977 as the "marketing, distribution, prescription and the use of drugs in the society with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social and economic consequences". The assessment of drug utilization is important for clinical, educational and pharmaco-economic purposes.¹

Drug utilization research provides insight to different aspects of drug use and drug prescribing such as pattern of use, quality of use and outcomes of drug use. Monitoring prescription and study of drug utilization could identify the associated problems and provide feedback to the practitioner so as to create awareness about the rational use of drugs. Drug utilization evaluation was originally known as the drug utilization review (DUR) in the 1970s. The term drug utilization review (DUR) and the drug use evaluation (DUE) are interchangeable. The process is divided into four phases: planning, data collection and evaluation, intervention, and program evaluation.¹

Studies on the process of drug utilization focus on factors related to prescribing, dispensing, administering and taking of medication and its associated events. Drug utilization play a significant role in helping the health-care system to understand, interpret and improve the prescribing administration and use of medications.²

The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification System with Defined Daily Doses (ATC/DDD).

The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System is used for the classification of active ingredients of drugs according to the organ or system on which they act and their therapeutic, pharmacological and chemical properties.

The ATC/DDD system classifies therapeutic drugs. The purpose of the ATC/DDD system is to serve as a tool for drug utilization research in order to improve quality of drug use.

Defined Daily Dose (DDD)

The assumed average maintenance dose per day for a drug used for its main indication in adults.

$$\text{DDD}/1000 \text{ inhabitants/day} = \frac{\text{Total use of a drug (mg) during the study period} \times 100}{\text{DDD(mg)} \times \text{Duration of study} \times \text{Total sample size}}$$

Prescribed Daily Dose (PDD)

Prescribed Daily Dose (PDD) is the average daily amount of a drug that is actually prescribed. It can be calculated as the ratio of two rates, which can be age- and sex- adjusted using either the Manitoba population or the group of user proportions for the year of analysis and using a direct method of standardization.

PDD is calculated per person for solid dosage forms only (tablets and capsules).³

Lower respiratory tract infection

Lower respiratory tract infection is an acute illness (present for 21 days or less), usually with cough as the main symptom, with at least one other lower respiratory tract symptoms (sputum production, dyspnoea, wheeze or chest discomfort/pain) and no alternative explanation (e.g. sinusitis or asthma).

Worldwide, infants and children represent a higher proportion of the population. 28% of the world's total population is accounted for by children younger than 15 years of age. Pediatrics is the branch of science that deals with the medical care of infants, children and adolescents.² Infancy and childhood is a period of rapid growth and development. Compared to adult medicines, drug use in pediatric is not extensively researched and the range of licensed drugs and appropriate dosage form is limited.

Pediatric population is a spectrum of different physiologies and comprises subgroups differing by age as preterm neonates, full term neonates, infants and toddlers, and older children and adolescents. Significant changes in the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics occur as preterm infants mature towards term, as infants mature during the first few years of life, and as children reach puberty and adolescence. The bioavailability, pharmacodynamics, pharmacokinetics, efficacy and adverse effects can differ markedly between pediatrics and adult patients as well as among pediatric patients because of difference in age, organ function and disease state. Respiratory tract infection (RTI) is considered as one of the major public health problems in developing countries. It is recognized as the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in many developing countries. In developing countries 25% of all pediatric admissions are due to acute respiratory tract infections and which ultimately causes death of 3.5 million children each year.⁵ Lower respiratory tract infections are the leading cause of death in children below 5 years of age.⁶

Use of Antibiotic prescription in LRI remains controversial. On the one hand, it is usually of bacterial origin, is associated with a high morbidity and mortality, and needs to be rapidly treated with an antibiotic. On the other hand, in a case of LRI, it is difficult to exclude the diagnosis of community acquired pneumonia (CAP) in out-patients, and most of the times self-limiting illnesses, and prescription of antimicrobials may cause increased antimicrobial resistance. Because LRI is one of the major reasons for antibiotic treatment and because changes in antibiotic resistance patterns are a threat to its effective treatment, there is increasing concern about antibiotic prescription in the community.⁷ There are more effective drugs (medicines) today on the market than ever before. Patients are better educated, have greater expectations from health care, and they use multiple sources of health care. Still, drugs are not frequently used to their full potential or according to the generally accepted criteria. All prescribing may not necessarily be based on patient needs and all patient needs are not necessarily met with drug therapy. The development of drug utilization (DU) as a research area made it possible to study drug prescribing and drug usage in a scientific and formal manner.⁸

In developing countries 30% of all patients consultation and 25% of all pediatric admission are due to acute respiratory tract infections and which ultimately causes death of 3.5 million children each year.⁶ While antimicrobial drugs are responsible for some of the most dramatic improvements in medical therapy in history, these medicines are also the only class of drug whose efficacy diminishes with their wide-scale use in hospital-based and outpatient settings. The increased use of antimicrobial drugs has coincided with the emergence of antimicrobial resistance, which constitutes an important clinical, economic, and public health problem. Resistant pathogens increase healthcare associated expenses, complicate therapy and make treatment failure more often. Therefore, there has been a growing attentiveness to the rational use of antimicrobials since 1990s. The use of antibiotics has become a routine practice for the treatment of pediatric illnesses. Thus children and infants are subjected to in numerous discrepancies in antibiotic medications. Drug resistance is the reduction in effectiveness of a drug in curing a disease or improving a patient's symptoms and it is an important factor in the development of antibiotic resistance.⁹

Therefore Pediatric patients require more attention while prescribing medications in order to avoid the resistance, adverse drug reactions and drug-drug interactions. The study of prescribing pattern is a part of the medical audit and seeks to monitor, evaluate, and if necessary, suggest modifications in prescribing practices to make medical care rational and cost-effective.¹⁰

Acute respiratory tract infection (ARI) is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in both developing and developed countries.¹⁰ WHO recognized respiratory diseases as the second important cause of death for children under five years in 2010.¹¹ WHO states that pneumonia is one of the main three causes for newborn infant deaths.¹² Pneumonia was diagnosed in approximately 156 million children in 2008 (151 million in developing countries and 5 million in developed countries) and led to 1.4 million deaths (28-34% of all deaths) in those younger than five years of age.¹¹ Mortality due to pneumonia accounts for approximately one-fourth of the total deaths in under five children, in India.¹³

Antimicrobials are considered as the greatest discovery of the twentieth century. In the pre-antibiotic era, infectious diseases accounted for significant morbidity and mortality and invasive medical procedures were fraught with the risk of infection. All this changed with the use of antimicrobial agents. But the miracle seems to be short lived. Irresponsible and erratic use of these life-saving instruments has resulted in the development of resistance in many organisms and a death due to hospital-acquired infections is on the rise. It appears that our complacency is leading us into bigger problems in the millennium that has just dawned.¹⁴

Emergence of antibiotic resistance is a worldwide phenomenon and it is due to over use of antibiotics. Increased self-prescribing, poor choice of antibiotics, not following routine susceptibility testing and inadequate surveillance are other factors contributing to development of antibiotic resistance.⁶

Antimicrobial resistance poses a serious threat to human health and welfare and undermines national economies worldwide. Annual losses stemming from antimicrobial resistance are estimated to range from 21000 million to 34000 million dollars in the United States of America.¹⁴

A report (August 2014) in the journal *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, said that in 2010, India consumed 13 billion units of antibiotics, the highest in the world. Between 2005 and 2009, consumption shot up by 40 percent. Between 2008 and 2013, E.coli bacteria resistant to third-generation cephalosporin increased from 70 to 83 per cent.

The irony is that at the same time, the lack of access or delayed access to effective antibiotics is causing more deaths in India than from drug-resistant bacteria. This is best revealed in the case of pneumonia in children less than five years of age. Most of the 1,70,000 pneumonia deaths that occurred in this age group in India in 2013 could have been averted had these children had access to effective antibiotics, notes a paper published on November 18, 2015 in the journal *The Lancet*. Only 12.5 per cent of affected children received antibiotic treatment for pneumonia.

One mechanism to ensure correct prescribing and use is the drug utilization review (DUR) process. The ultimate goal of this drug utilization study is to assess whether drug therapy is rational or not. This study may provide insights into the various aspects of drug use like pattern, quality, determinants and outcome along with drug prescribing. It also contributes to rational drug use in important ways like; Description of drug use patterns which increase understanding of how drugs are being used, early signals of irrational use of drugs which may generate hypothesis that set the agenda for further investigations and thus avoid prolonged irrational use of drugs, interventions to improve drug use - follow-up are under taken that may enable to assess whether interventions intended to improve drug use have had the desired impact.¹⁵

The present study aims to investigate the utilization patterns of antibiotics and the current prescribing practice for LRTI in Pediatric Department of a tertiary care hospital.

As clinical pharmacists, the aim of our study is to observe and analyze the prescribing and utilization pattern and the rationality of the antibiotics prescribed to the inpatients with LRTI in the Pediatric Department of SSIMS & RC.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the prescribing and utilization pattern of antibiotics prescribed to the patients with LRTI admitted in the Pediatric Department.
- To identify the commonly prescribed antibiotics in patients with LRTI in the Pediatric Department.
- To identify sensitivity and resistance pattern of the organism causing LRTI.
- To identify the number of drugs prescribed by generic and brand name.
- To identify the drug interactions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Materials used:**

- Informed Assent Form
- Patient Data Collection Form

Study design:

A Prospective observational study.

Ethical issues:

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Methods:

A Prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere. Data of pediatric patients collected from the Pediatric ward were included in the study. The collected data was analyzed using Microsoft excel. The DDD/1000 inhabitants/day was also calculated. The medication order problem like possible drug-drug interaction is also evaluated.

RESULTS

After proper examination, using the exclusion and inclusion criteria, 150 patients were enrolled in the study.

Table 1: Sex wise distribution of cases.

ILLNESS	CASES (%)	MALE (%)	FEMALE (%)
BRONCHIOLITIS	9(6)	5(55.56)	4(44.44)
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	5(3.33)	3(60)	2(40)
LRTI	20(13.33)	14(70)	6(30)
PNEUMONIA	97(64.67)	53(54.64)	44(45.36)
WALRI	19(12.67)	13(68.42)	6(31.58)
TOTAL	150(100)	88(58.67)	62(41.33)

Out of the 150 patients, 88 patients (58.7%) were males and 62 patients (32.1%) were females.

Table 2: Associated illness.

ILLNESS	ANAEMIA	SEIZURE	ASOM	TOF	DIARRHOEA	HEPATITIS
BRONCHIOLITIS	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	0	0	0	0	0	0
LRTI	2	0	0	0	0	0
PNEUMONIA	6	2	1	1	1	1
WALRI	0		0	0	0	0

In our study, out of the 150 cases collected, 14 cases were found along with co-morbidities. Anaemia was the most commonly found associated illness. A total of 8 cases of anaemia were found. Seizure was the second most commonly found associated illness.

Table 3: Average hospital stay and no: of antibiotics prescribed.

ILLNESS	TOTAL NO. OF HOSPITAL DAYS	AVERAGE HOSPITAL STAY	TOTAL NO. OF ANTIBIOTICS USED	AVERAGE NO:OF ANTIBIOTICS USED
BRONCHIOLITIS	45	5.8±2.3	9	1
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	24	5.3±2.3	13	2.6
LRTI	111	5.4±2.3	23	1.15
PNEUMONIA	585	5.7±2.3	120	1.26
WALRI	88	5.4±2.3	20	1.05
TOTAL	853	5.7±2.3	185	1.23

In our study, for the 150 cases collected, the average hospital stay was 5.7 days with a standard deviation of 2.3. In our study, total number of antibiotics prescribed was 185 and the average number of antibiotics per prescription was 1.23.

Table 4: Drugs prescribed in oral route and parenteral route.

ILLNESS	DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN PARENTERAL ROUTE (%)	DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN ORAL ROUTE (%)
BRONCHIOLITIS	9	0
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	13	0
LRTI	22	1
PNEUMONIA	114	6
WALRI	20	0
TOTAL	178 (96.22)	7 (3.78)

In our study, a total of 185 antibiotics were prescribed. In that 178 (96.22%) were prescribed through parenteral route and 7(3.78%) were prescribed through oral route.

Table 5: Number and percentage of culture sensitivity performed.

ILLNESS	TOTAL NO. OF CULTURE SENSITIVITY PERFORMED	PERCENTAGE OF CULTURE SENSITIVITY PERFORMED (%)
BRONCHIOLITIS	0	0
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	0	0
LRTI	0	0
PNEUMONIA	14	14.43%
WALRI	0	0
TOTAL, n = 150	14	9.33%

In our study, out of the 150 cases collected, only 14 cases (10.7%) were subjected to culture sensitivity test. In that only 2 organism were isolated.

Table 6: Organism isolated with its resistance and sensitivity pattern.

Organism isolated	Resistant to	Sensitive to
Enterococcus faecalis	Ampicillin, Clindamycin, Erythromycin, Gentamycin, Penicillin G, Tetracyclin	Levofloxacin, Linezolid, Moxifloxacin, Nitrofurantoin, Vancomycin,
Streptococcus species	Cotrimoxazole, Doxycycline, Erythromycin, Penicillin G, Cefoxitin	Clindamycin, Linezolid, Moxifloxacin, Vancomycin

Table 7: Distribution of individual antibiotics.

Drug	Bronchiolitis	Bronchopneumonia (%)	LRTI	Pneumonia	WALRI	TOTAL (%)
Penicillins						
Amoxicillin	9	2	10	59	9	89(48.11)
Piperacillin	0	1	0	0	0	1(0.54)
Cephalosporins						
Ceftriaxone	0	3	8	32	11	54(29.20)
Cefotaxime	0	2	1	5	0	8(4.32)
Macrolide						
Azithromycin	0	2	3	19	0	24(12.97)
Tetracycline antibiotic						
Doxycycline	0	0	0	1	0	1(0.54)
Aminoglycoside						
Amikacin	0	2	1	4	0	7(3.78)
Oxazolidinones						
Linezolid	0	1	0	0	0	1(0.54)
TOTAL	9	13	23	120	20	185(100)

In our study, out of the 185 antibiotics prescribed, the most commonly prescribed antibiotic was Amoxicillin (48.1%) followed by Ceftriaxone (29.20%).

Table 8: ATC code,DDD,PDD and DDDs/1000 inhabitants/day.

Drug	ATC code	DDD (mg)	PDD(mg)	DDD/1000 inhabitants/day
Penicillins				
Amoxicillin	J01CA04	1000	635.4	2.09
Piperacillin	J01CR05	14000	13500	0.036
Cephalosporins				
Ceftriaxone	J01DD04	2000	586.1	0.059
Cefotaxime	J01DD01	4000	328.1	0.025
Macrolide				
Azithromycin	J01FA10	300	246.7	0.730
Tetracycline antibiotic				
Doxycycline	J01AA02	100	100	0.037
Aminoglycoside				
Amikacin	J01GB06	1000	77.9	0.020
Oxazolidone				
Linezolid	J01XX08	1200	360	0.011

Table 9: Comparison of PDD and DDD.

PDD>DDD	PDD<DDD	PDD=DDD
-	Amikacin	Doxycycline
-	Azithromycin	
-	Linezolid	
-	Amoxicillin	
-	Ceftriaxone	
-	Cefotaxime	

DDD and PDD of the antibiotics were compared.

Table 9: No. of antibiotics prescribed in brand name and generic name.

ILLNESS	BRAND NAME	GENERIC NAME
BRONCHIOLITIS	9	0
BRONCHOPNEUMONIA	9	4
LRTI	22	1
PNEUMONIA	112	8
WALRI	20	0
TOTAL	172	13
TOTAL NO. OF DRUGS = 185		

In our study most of the drugs were prescribed by brand names. Out of the total 185 antibiotics prescribed, only 13 drugs (7%) were prescribed by generic names and 172 drugs (93%) were prescribed by brand names.

Table 10: No. of drug interactions.

TYPE OF INTERACTIONS	NUMBERS
MAJOR	4
MODERATE	9
MINOR	25

In our study, a total of 38 interactions were found. Out of which 4 were major, 9 were moderate and 25 minor interactions were found. The major interaction was between Azithromycin and Ondansetron.

DISCUSSION

Worldwide, infants and children represent a higher proportion of the population. Pediatrics is the branch of science that deals with the medical care of infants, children and adolescents.² Infancy and childhood is a period of rapid growth and development. Compared to adult medicines, drug use in pediatric is not extensively researched and the range of licensed drugs and appropriate dosage form is limited. Therefore limited data are available in general, and in India in particular, on drug utilization on this population. In our study, a total of 150 cases are studied. Out of the 150 cases, 88 patients (58.67%) were males and 62 patients (41.33%) were females. It was similar to a study conducted by N.Venkateshwaramurthy et al.¹⁷

In our study, the most commonly found associated illness was found to be anemia. A similar result was observed in a study conducted by Harish GN.¹⁸ A total of 8 cases with anemia as the associated illness was found. The presence of co morbidities leads to multiple and complex drug therapy and thus chances of drug interactions and ADR are greater.

In our study the average hospital stay was 5.7 days with a standard deviation of 2.3. A similar result was found in a study conducted by Stimson Jose et al.¹⁶ But in contrast to this a higher value of 8.9 days were obtained in a study conducted by Choudhury DK et al.²⁹

In our study, total number of antibiotics prescribed was 185 and the average number of antibiotics per prescription was 1.23. In a similar study conducted by Deshmukh et al, the average number of antibiotics per prescription was 2.16 which is comparatively little higher to our study.²⁶ Usage of more than the required number of antibiotics per patient will increase the cost of the therapy, risk of adverse effects, drug interactions, emergence and resistance and may also contribute to non-compliance by the patients. Therefore, it is preferable to keep the number of drugs as low as possible.

In our study, a total of 185 antibiotics were prescribed. In that 178 (96.22%) were prescribed through parenteral route and 7(3.78%) were prescribed through oral route. A similar result was observed in a study conducted by Kokani VR et al.³⁴ WHO recommends lesser use of injection as it is helpful in reducing the cost of the treatment and its disadvantages. But some factors facilitate the use of this route. In oral dosage forms the most commonly used dosage form was syrup. Children are comfortable with dosage forms like syrup and drops compared to tablets and capsules. It increases compliance and helps in completing the treatment regimen.

In our study, out of the 150 cases collected, only 14 cases (14.43%) were subjected to culture sensitivity test. As the number of culture sensitivity performed was very low, the sensitivity and resistance pattern of the organism were not analyzed properly. This result is very lower when compared to a result in study conducted by Harish GN et al.¹⁸ The decrease in the percentage of culture might be based on the clinical presentation at the time of admission. A study conducted by K Shamsy et al showed that only 5.13% of cases were subjected to culture sensitivity test.²¹ Before the initiation of antimicrobials it is necessary to isolate from the specimen and identify the causative organism for appropriate antimicrobial therapy. Antibiotic usage mainly depends on various factors like resistance, adverse effects and cost of the health care. So, proper methods should be implemented in order to prevent the irrational use of antibiotics like proper understanding of therapeutic use of antibiotics, awareness about prevalence of various pathogens and resistance patterns to advice the proper empirical therapy.

In our study, the most commonly prescribed antibiotic was Amoxicillin (48.11%) followed by Ceftriaxone (29.20%). This finding was similar to a study conducted by Shruthi KV et al. Whereas in another study conducted by Divya K et al, Cephalosporins were most commonly prescribed class of antibiotic followed by Macrolides.²⁰ The antibiotics used in the hospital were of older generation antibiotics and this has to be welcomed.

Drug consumption data was expressed as defined daily dose (DDD) per 1000 inhabitants per day. The highest value of 2.09 was DDD/1000 inhabitants/day was accounted for Amoxicillin indicating that it was the popular drug of choice, followed by Azithromycin with a value of 0.730 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day. In a similar study conducted by Harish GN et al, the highest value of 5.74 DDD/1000inhabitants/day was accounted for Azithromycin followed by Ceftriaxone with the value of 5.24 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day.¹⁸

In our study most of the drugs were prescribed by brand names. Out of the total 185 antibiotics prescribed, only 13 drugs (7%) were prescribed by generic names and 172 drugs (93%) were prescribed by brand names. Similar observations were made by Ravika K et al.²² The possible reasons for nominal use of generic drugs could be that the branded drugs are easily available and the next possible reason may be vigorous promotional strategies by the pharmaceutical companies. Prescribing by generic name helps the hospital pharmacy to have better inventory control. These will also aid the pharmacy to purchase the drugs on contract bias, as the number of brand is less, reduce confusion among the pharmacist while dispensing. Generic drugs are often more economic than the branded ones.

In our study, a total of 38 interactions were found. In that 4 major, 9 moderate and 25 minor interactions were found. The major interaction was between Azithromycin and Ondansetron. A similar interaction was found in a study conducted by Jimmy OD et al.⁴⁵

CONCLUSION

LRTIs are common among the pediatric patients. The present study was carried out in order to assess the utilization pattern of antibiotics for the treatment of LRTI in the Pediatric Department of a tertiary care teaching hospital. This study provides an insight to the commonly prescribed antibiotics and evaluation of drug drug interactions.

In our study out of 150 cases males were more than females. The commonly found associated illness was anaemia. The average hospital stay was 5.7 ± 2.3 days. Out of 150 cases, only 14 (14.43%) cases were subjected for the culture sensitivity. In our study, the total number of antibiotics prescribed was 185 and the average number of antibiotics per prescription was 1.23. Amoxicillin was found to be the most common antibiotic prescribed, followed by Ceftriaxone. Most of the drugs were prescribed in the generic name. That is, 96.22% of the drugs were prescribed through parenteral route and 3.78% were prescribed through oral route. The PDD and DDD of the antibiotics were also compared. Most of the drugs were prescribed in brand name. Only 7% of the drugs were prescribed in the generic name. In our study, a total of 38 interactions were found. In that 4 were major, 9 were moderate and 25 minor interactions were found.

In general practice, the therapeutic approach for lower respiratory tract infection is primarily empirical and the main aim of the physicians is to treat as specifically as possible. The present study indicates the general trends of the use of antibiotics in lower respiratory tract infection in pediatric department.

Drug utilization studies have the potential to make objective evaluation and analysis of health professionals work and provide them with feedback to stimulate thinking about their practice and looking for ways to improve their own performance. These studies should become a method of increasing job satisfaction and means of education for health professionals, rather than being perceived as threat or another bureaucratic burden. Antibiotic resistance is an emerging problem and has become a major threat to the medical field. Excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotic has been a major contributor to this ever growing problem.

To conclude, it is evident from the present study that, in Pediatric Department, for lower respiratory tract infections the most commonly used antibiotic was Amoxicillin followed by Ceftriaxone. Prescribing by generic names has to be encouraged.

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